

Effects of Extracurricular Physics Activities on Senior Secondary School Students' Learning Outcomes in Physics in Osun State

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Abstract:

The study investigated the effects of Extracurricular Physics Activities on senior secondary school students' learning outcomes in Physics in Osun State. A quasi-experimental pre-test and post-test two-group design was adopted. The target population comprised 76,885 Senior Secondary School Two science students in public secondary schools in Osun State. A sample of 133 Physics students from six intact classes in six public secondary schools in Osun State was selected using a multistage sampling procedure. Data were collected using a validated Performance Test in Physics (PTP) and Physics Attitudinal Scale (PAS), with reliability coefficients of 0.80 and 0.82 confirmed respectively through Cronbach Alpha. Analysis involved frequency counts, percentages, means, standard deviations, and t-tests. Findings revealed no significant difference in pre-test performance mean scores and attitudes of students exposed to Extracurricular Physics Activities and conventional methods before treatment. However, significant differences were observed in post-test performance mean scores and attitudes of students exposed to Extracurricular Physics Activities compared to the conventional method. The results indicate that while both groups were similar at the outset, Extracurricular Physics Activities proved more effective in enhancing students' understanding and attitudes toward Physics. The study concludes that incorporating Extracurricular Physics Activities in secondary school Physics classes can improve academic performance and foster positive attitudes. It is recommended that teachers adopt such activities to strengthen students' engagement and achievement in Physics.

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Introduction

Science education is fundamental to Nigeria's socio-economic and technological development. It equips citizens with the knowledge and skills required for innovation, critical thinking, and problem-solving, all of which are essential for addressing national challenges such as poverty, insecurity, public health, and environmental degradation (Olojo et al., 2022). Through quality science education, Nigeria can advance key sectors such as agriculture, healthcare, and renewable energy, while also enhancing national security by improving public understanding of disease prevention, environmental sustainability, and resource management (Iredia, 2011). A strong foundation in science further enables Nigeria to participate meaningfully in global knowledge networks, research collaborations, and technological exchanges. Consequently, prioritizing science education through teacher training, curriculum reforms, and improved facilities is essential for national growth (Olojo et al., 2022; Iredia, 2011). Physics, a core branch of science, provides the conceptual basis for disciplines such as engineering, medicine, ICT, space science, and other technological fields. Its curriculum is built around major concepts—including motion, energy, waves, fields, and quanta organized to help learners understand how matter and energy interact in the physical world.

However, the teaching and learning of physics in Nigeria remain problematic. Students frequently struggle with fundamental concepts such as waves, electricity, magnetism, nuclear physics, simple harmonic motion, and energy quantization (Okeke, 2019; Erinsho, 2016). These challenges are compounded by students' misconceptions, which persist when instruction is teacher-centered and does not actively address prior beliefs (Driver et al., 2012). Conceptual Change Pedagogy has been suggested as a strategy for correcting these misunderstandings, thereby improving students' learning outcomes. WAEC reports (2020–2024) indicate persistent weaknesses in Nigerian students' conceptual understanding and problem-solving abilities in physics (Avbenagha, 2024). These difficulties are linked to both instructional methods and students' general attitudes toward the subject.

Extracurricular activities such as science clubs, field trips, physics exhibitions, quiz competitions, and laboratory demonstrations provide students with practical and engaging experiences outside the formal classroom environment. These activities encourage hands-on learning, collaboration, creativity, and exploration of physics concepts beyond the syllabus. Research consistently shows that extracurricular engagement enhances students' interest, motivation, and academic performance. Nelson and Oragwu (2023) reported that extracurricular participation improves students' involvement and learning outcomes. Adeyemo (2010) also found a positive link between extracurricular participation and students' achievement in physics. In Osun State, such activities can make physics more approachable, relatable, and enjoyable, thereby addressing the perception of physics as abstract and difficult.

International evidence also supports these findings. For example, Al-qatawneh (2020) demonstrated that extracurricular programs significantly increased learners' motivation to study physics among Jordanian secondary students. Similarly, Fitriyana et al. (2025) found that physics clubs help strengthen students' physics identity, confidence, and sense of belonging, all of which shape positive attitudes toward the subject.

Students' attitudes toward physics are central to their learning outcomes. Attitude encompasses a learner's interest, motivation, beliefs, and perceptions about a subject. In Nigeria, many students hold negative attitudes toward physics, often viewing it as overly

abstract or disconnected from everyday life (Jegede & Awodun, 2015; Nelson & Oragwu, 2023). These attitudes are influenced by teacher-centered instruction, insufficient practical activities, and limited exposure to real-world applications. Extracurricular physics activities can counteract negative attitudes by giving students opportunities to interact with physics concepts in enjoyable and meaningful ways. Jegede and Awodun (2015) showed that outdoor physics activities significantly improved students' attitudes in Ekiti State. When students participate in field trips, hands-on demonstrations, and competitions, they develop greater confidence and interest in the subject. Improved attitudes often correspond with improved academic achievement. Avbenagha (2024) established that laboratory-assisted and activity-based methods enhanced both attitudes and performance among physics students in Delta State. This suggests that extracurricular activities which are inherently practical can provide alternative pathways for meaningful learning in contexts where laboratories or instructional resources are limited.

Despite their benefits, extracurricular physics programs face numerous constraints in Nigeria. Many schools lack funding, equipment, functional laboratories, and trained staff to support such activities. In Osun State, resource limitations hinder the organization of consistent extracurricular programs. Some teachers also view extracurricular physics activities as distractions from the formal curriculum, while students may hesitate to participate due to academic pressure or lack of encouragement. Addressing these challenges requires deliberate policy support, capacity-building for teachers, partnerships with industries and science-based organizations, and community involvement to sustain extracurricular initiatives.

Physics remains the backbone of technological and scientific progress, yet students in Nigeria continue to struggle with conceptual understanding and achievement. Extracurricular physics activities offer a practical solution by enhancing motivation, correcting misconceptions, and fostering positive attitudes toward physics. Evidence from Nigeria and other countries demonstrates that these activities significantly improve students' interest, engagement, and performance. In Osun State, where schools often grapple with inadequate facilities and teacher-centered instructional approaches, extracurricular physics programs can provide an essential complement to classroom teaching. Strengthening such programs requires investment, collaboration, and sustained institutional support. When effectively implemented, extracurricular activities can help bridge gaps in physics education and contribute to national goals of scientific literacy and technological advancement.

Statement of the Problem

Physics is a key subject for preparing students for STEM careers, yet students in Osun State consistently perform poorly in it. One possible factor influencing this performance is participation in extracurricular activities such as sports, clubs, and cultural groups. Although these activities are believed to support students' overall development, there is debate about whether they help or hinder academic achievement, especially in challenging subjects like physics. Some believe extracurricular involvement boosts motivation and cognitive skills, while others argue it may distract from academics and reduce study time. In Osun State, there is little research specifically examining how extracurricular physics activities affect physics learning outcomes. This lack of evidence makes it difficult for educators and policymakers to decide whether such activities should be encouraged or regulated. The study therefore aims to address this gap by investigating the effects of extracurricular Physics activities on students' physics performance.

The purpose of this study was to investigate the Effects of Extracurricular Physics Activities on Senior Secondary Schools' Students 'Learning Outcomes in Physics in Osun State.

. Specifically, the objectives of the study are to determine:

- i. the performance of students in Physics exposed to Extracurricular Physics Activities and conventional method
- ii. the attitude of students towards Physics exposed to Extracurricular Physics Activities and conventional method
- iii. the significant difference in the pre-test performance mean score of students in Extracurricular Physics Activities and conventional method.
- iv. the significant difference in the attitude of students exposed to Extracurricular Physics Activities and conventional method before treatment.
- v. the significant difference in the post-test performance mean scores of students exposed to Extracurricular Physics Activities and conventional method.
- vi. the significant difference in the attitude of students exposed to Extracurricular Physics Activities and conventional method after treatment.

The following research questions guided the study:

1. What are the effects of Extracurricular Physics Activities and conventional method on the performance of students in Physics before and after the treatment?
2. What is the attitude of students towards Physics exposed to Extracurricular Physics Activities and conventional method before and after the treatment?

The following null hypotheses were generated for this study:

1. There is no significant difference in the pre-test performance mean score of students in Extracurricular Physics Activities and conventional method.
2. There is no significant difference in the attitude of students exposed to Extracurricular Physics Activities and conventional method before treatment.
3. There is no significant difference in the post-test performance mean scores of students exposed to Extracurricular Physics Activities and conventional method.
4. There is no significant difference in the attitude of students exposed to Extracurricular Physics Activities and conventional method after treatment.

Methodology

This study employed a quasi-experimental pre-test and post-test two-group design. The target population comprised 76,885 Senior Secondary School Two science students in public secondary schools in Osun State. A sample of 133 Physics students was selected using a multistage sampling procedure. First, one Senatorial District was chosen at random, followed by two Local Government Areas. From each Local Government Area, three public secondary schools were selected, and intact S.S.S. 2 classes from four schools were used. Schools were randomly assigned to experimental and control groups.

A one-day workshop was organized for research assistants who facilitated the Extracurricular Physics Activities. Two instruments were used: the Performance Test in Physics (PTP) and the Physics Attitudinal Scale (PAS). The PTP measured achievement in Physics and consisted of 30 questions covering motion and projectile, administered as both pre-test and post-test (with reshuffled items to avoid carry-over effects). The PAS assessed students' attitudes toward Physics using 20 items on a four-point Likert scale (Strongly Agree to Strongly Disagree). Both instruments were validated by experts in Tests and Measurement, Physics teachers, and the two expert from Science Technology and Mathematics Education. Reliability

was confirmed using Cronbach Alpha, yielding coefficients of 0.80 for PTP and 0.82 for PAS respectively.

The study was conducted in three phases:

- ❖ Phase I (Pre-treatment): Pre-test instruments administered to both groups to establish homogeneity.
- ❖ Phase II (Treatment): Experimental group received one hour of extracurricular Physics lessons weekly for four weeks, covering motion and projectile. The control group was taught the same topics using conventional classroom methods.
- ❖ Phase III (Post-treatment): PTP and PAS were re-administered to measure the effects of the intervention.

Both descriptive and inferential statistics were applied to the instrument for data analysis. The research questions were answered using mean, and standard deviation, The hypotheses 1-4 were tested using t-test All the hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance.

Results

Research Question 1: What are the effects of Extracurricular Physics Activities and conventional method on the performance of students in Physics before and after the treatment?

Table 1: Mean and standard deviation of pre-test and post-test scores of students in experimental and control groups

Strategies	Test	N	Mean	S.D	Mean Diff.
Extracurricular Physics Activities	Pre-test	74	44.70	2.58	38.59
	Post-test		83.29	4.51	
Conventional method	Pre-test	59	44.30	2.47	3.90
	Post-test		48.20	2.04	
Total		133			

Table 1 revealed that pre-test performance mean scores of students exposed to Extracurricular Physics Activities was 44.70 while conventional method was 44.30 with their corresponding standard deviations as 2.58 and 2.47 respectively in Physics. The post-test performance mean scores of students exposed to Extracurricular Physics Activities was 83.29 and conventional method was 48.20 with their corresponding standard deviations as 4.51 and 2.04 respectively in Physics. The mean difference in Extracurricular Physics Activities was found to be 38.59 while that of the conventional method group was found to be 3.90.

This implied that the use of Extracurricular Physics Activities had significant effects on the performance of students in Physics before and after treatments which was depicted in figure i.

Figure i: Bar chart on the performance of students before and after treatments in Physics
Research Question 2: What is the attitude of students towards Physics exposed to Extracurricular Physics Activities and conventional method Before and after the treatment?

Table 2: Mean and standard deviation of pre-test and post-test scores of students in experimental and control groups

Strategies	Test	N	Mean	S.D	Mean Diff.
Extracurricular Physics Activities	Pre-test	74	44.12	4.67	31.50
	Post-test		75.62	4.70	
Conventional method	Pre-test	59	44.93	4.77	17.68
	Post-test		62.61	3.90	
Total		133			

Table 2 revealed that the attitude of students exposed to Extracurricular Physics Activities was 44.12 while conventional method was 44.93 with their corresponding standard deviations as 4.67 and 4.77 respectively in Physics. The post-test performance mean scores of students exposed to Extracurricular Physics Activities was 75.62 and conventional method was 62.61 with their corresponding standard deviations as 4.70 and 3.90 respectively in Computer studies. The mean difference in Extracurricular Physics Activities was found to be 31.50 while that of the conventional method group was found to be 17.68.

This implied that the attitude of students in the use of Extracurricular Physics Activities had effects on the performance of students in Physics before and after treatments which was depicted in figure i.

Testing of Hypotheses

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant difference in the pre-test performance mean scores of students exposed to Extracurricular Physics Activities and conventional method.

Students' pre-treatment performance was analysed using t-test for statistical significance at the 0.05 level of significance to test the hypothesis. Table 3 displays the final result.

Table 3: t-test analysis for pre-test performance mean scores of students exposed to Extracurricular Physics Activities and conventional method.

Variations	N	Mean	SD	df	t _{cal}	P (Sig)	Rem.
Extracurricular Physics Activities	74	44.70	2.58	131	0.898	0.371	Not Significant
Conventional method	59	44.30	2.47				

P>0.05

Table 3 shows that the t-cal value of 0.898 is not significant because the P value (0.371) > 0.05 at 0.05 level of significance. This implies that null hypothesis is not rejected. Hence, there is no significant difference in the pre-test performance mean scores of students exposed to Extracurricular Physics Activities and conventional method.. By implication, the students in the experimental and control groups were homogeneous at the commencement of the study.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant difference in the attitude of students exposed to Extracurricular Physics Activities and conventional method before treatment.

Students' pre-treatment attitudes was analysed using t-test for statistical significance at the 0.05 level of significance to test the hypothesis. Table 4 shows the final result.

Table 4: t-test analysis for difference in the attitude of students exposed to Extracurricular Physics Activities and conventional method before treatment in Physics

Variations	N	Mean	SD	df	t _{cal}	P (Sig)	Rem.
Extracurricular Physics Activities	74	44.12	4.67	131	0.984	0.327	Not Significant
Conventional method	59	44.93	4.77				

P>0.05

Table 4 shows that the t-cal value of 0.984 is not significant because the P value (0.327) > 0.05 at 0.05 level of significance. This implies that null hypothesis is not rejected. Hence, there is no significant difference in the attitude of students exposed to Extracurricular Physics Activities and conventional method before treatment. By implication, the students in the experimental and control groups were homogeneous at the commencement of the study.

Hypothesis 3: There is no significant difference in the post-test performance mean scores of students exposed to Extracurricular Physics Activities and conventional method.

Students' post-test performance was analysed using t-test statistical analysis at 0.05 level of significance.

Table 5: t-test analysis for post-test performance of students exposed to Extracurricular Physics Activities and Conventional Method.

Variations	N	Mean	SD	df	t	P
Extracurricular Physics Activities	75	82.85	5.90	140	46.15	0.00*
Conventional method	67	48.26	1.73			

*p<0.05

Table 5 shows that p value (0.00) < α value (0.05). This implies that null hypothesis was rejected. Hence, there was a significant difference in the post-test performance mean scores of students exposed to Extracurricular Physics Activities and Conventional Method. By implication, the mean score showed a significant difference of 34.59 in favour of students

exposed to Extracurricular Physics Activities. Students exposed to Extracurricular Physics Activities performed better than students taught with Conventional method.

Hypothesis 4: There is no significant difference in the attitude of students exposed to Extracurricular Physics Activities and conventional method after treatment.

Students' post-treatment attitudes was analysed using t-test for statistical significance at the 0.05 level of significance to test the hypothesis. Table 6 shows the final result.

Table 6: t-test analysis for difference in the attitude of students exposed to Extracurricular Physics Activities and Conventional Method after treatment

Variations	N	Mean	SD	df	T	P
Extracurricular Physics Activities	75	75.43	4.96	140	16.18	0.00*
Conventional method	67	63.49	3.62			

*p<0.05

Table 6 shows that p value (0.00) < α value (0.05). This implies that the null hypothesis was rejected. Hence, there is significant difference in the attitude of students exposed to Extracurricular Physics Activities and Conventional Method after the treatment. By implication, the attitudinal mean score showed a significant difference of 11.94 in favour students exposed to Extracurricular Physics Activities. Students exposed to Extracurricular Physics Activities had better attitude towards Physics when compared with the students in the Conventional method.

Discussion

The findings of the study revealed that there was no significant difference in the pre-test performance mean score of students in Extracurricular Physics Activities and conventional method. This proved that students in both groups were homogeneous before the treatment. In other words, the two groups were at the same level of performance in Physics.

The study also revealed that there was no significant difference in the attitude of students exposed to Extracurricular Physics Activities and conventional method before treatment. This proved that students in both groups were homogeneous before the treatment. In other words, the two groups were at the same attitudinal level in Physics.

A comparison of post-test performance mean scores between students who were taught using the Extracurricular Physics Activities and the Conventional Method showed a statistically significant difference. The top Physics grades were earned by those students who had been exposed to the Extracurricular Physics Activities. This was consistent with the claims of Al-qatawneh (2020) who investigated Effect of Extracurricular Activities on Generate Motivation for Learning Physics Students Practical Study on Secondary Students in Public Schools in Karak Province Extracurricular program including sports, games, art, music, drama, poetry applied to 10th-grade physics students in Jordan; compared experimental vs control (30 students each). The study found significant positive impact: students in the extracurricular-activity group showed higher motivation for learning physics than control. The authors concluded such activities help boost motivation for physics learning.

Students' attitude shifted dramatically after being exposed to either the Extracurricular Physics Activities or the Conventional Method, as evidenced by the outcomes. This findings was consistent with the submission of Fitriyana, et al. (2025) explored "Physics Club"

program to strengthen high school students' physics identity, Implementation of a non-formal physics club (extracurricular context) using developed club modules for high school students.

The physics-club programme tools were found valid and practical; the authors report that such non-formal context supports strengthening of students' "physics identity," which implies improved attitude, sense of belonging and identification with physics.

The findings of the study revealed that:

1. There was no significant difference in the pre-test performance mean score of students in Extracurricular Physics Activities and conventional method.
2. There was no significant difference in the attitude of students exposed to Extracurricular Physics Activities and conventional method before treatment.
3. There was significant difference in the post-test performance mean scores of students exposed to Extracurricular Physics Activities and conventional method.
4. There was significant difference in the attitude of students exposed to Extracurricular Physics Activities and conventional method after treatment.

Conclusion and Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, it could be concluded that at the outset of the trial, the two groups (Extracurricular Physics Activities and conventional method) were similar. Extracurricular Physics Activities outperformed the Conventional Method in improving the students' understanding of Physics with Extracurricular Physics Activities being the most effective strategy. Based on the findings of this study, it was recommended that the use of Extracurricular Physics Activities should be encouraged in Physics class in secondary schools so as to enhance better academic performance of students.

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